

Conjoint Analysis for a New Furniture Development

Venkatesh S. Amin¹, Anil Kumar² and Shasidhar Kotian³

1 Research Scholar, Institute of Management & Commerce, Srinivas University, Mangalore - 575001, India.

OrcidID: 0000-0003-1408-2323; E-mail: vnkymangalore@gmail.com

2 Research Professor, Institute of Management & Commerce, Srinivas University, Mangalore - 575001, India. OrcidID: 0000-0002-6736-8649; E-mail: anilkumar@gmail.com

3 Professor, Srinivas University, Mangalore-575001, India, E-Mail: mskot_70@yahoo.co.in

ABSTRACT:

New products are essential for any manufacturer and new products should be based on the requirements of the end customer. New furniture; a study table for students can create a new market as all students; few may not be in a position to afford the same. Hence there is a need for a study table that addresses the student community; be it at a hostel or home use. A new product is a gamble and is as complex as winning or losing a game or an event. The outcome is not guaranteed unless it is backed up by research from through a ground reality. A new product can generate better revenues that can lead to higher investments in the research and development of a few more products. New products are fundamentally new thoughts. Thoughts emerge due to challenges and these challenges are overcome when extrapolated with various combinations. One such combination is the conjoint analysis for new products that could be engaged for connecting or adding odd alternatives to form a new output. The resulting output will have a synergetic relationship greater than the individual components. This is an attempt to understand two sets of things; one the student community and two the need for a product that could enhance their academic output; thus a study table, that can catapult their academic performance.

Key words: New product development, Conjoint analysis, ideation, new markets, study table, SWOC analysis.

1.INTRODUCTION:

Furniture manufacturing requires design and development. Design is based on the need for a product. The design is first generated in the minds of the customer. The customer gives an idea of what he or she needs when it comes to the customization of furniture. Once a basic drawing is ready it needs to be developed using 2D or 3D drawing through a computer interface. Softwares enable a designer to come up with a drawing that enables the entire team to bring the final team ready. A design is created based on the needs of the customer. This is a kind of customization. Mass customization is the key to faster growth. Mass customization is possible when a market is studied and understood. The success of a student depends on the infrastructure and the availability of resources at his disposal. Hence it is understood that a good study

table creates comfort and faster learning as things are well organized and can be handy when required. Customer needs are changing and hence new products do fail and finding out a mantra that can create a successful new product is a challenge [1]. Different types of study tables can create different outputs. Based on the objective of the output a variety of study tables can be developed [2]. The classroom should motivate a student and similarly, a home study table should also motivate the same [3]. Sitting and standing positions while studying should be taken care and the study table should be adjustable to avoid back pain and reduce interest in studying [4]. The library makes a major impact on student life, study tables in a library should enhance the learning and development process it also should lead a student to research areas, hence the study tables in the library should be well designed as per the average student body mass index [5]. Houses today are too small and hence we need foldable furniture to a large extent. If a study table can be dismantled or expandable it would help students living in tiny houses to work and study comfortably [6]. New Product Development requires constant hard work and deep thinking. Every

2. OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY: The objective of the study is to learn the scope and business opportunity for a manufacturer to manufacture a study table. As there is demand, one needs to understand what type of table and what key attributes are required while making the study table should be kept in mind. This enhances the chances of selling to a large group of students who need it daily. The objective is also to understand what features students like to have in their study table. The weight of a study table is an essential component of the features that should be looked into. The study table should carry the weight and should be ergonomically designed [7][8]. New product brings hope; a ray of new hope to lead the market, to get new market share, and indeed survival.

2.1 Student study table as home furniture: Every student needs a certain infrastructure at home to work upon, a good study table should comprise of the following: sufficient space to keep all the books, space to spread books and study, a color that attracts and motivate a student to study as well as space that it can occupy and within a given budget. In general, there could be many attributes that parents and students would be interested in a study table for their wards. Those attributes would be the following in nature: Space, size, material, price and warranty, installation, locker keys, number of drawers, carrying weight, ease of dismantling, color, finishing, height, and compatibility with the chair.

3. RESEARCH TOOLS: A questionnaire is designed to know the market demand and the optimum price that it can command over the best features including durability and longevity. The most important aspect of the questionnaire is to understand the average ranking that the student community would give to the attributes that could be added to form a new study table. Conjoint analysis or conjoint measurement is a tool created by Prof. Paul Green on a basis to support the industry and the academia to come out with optimum solutions coupled with MDS (Multidimensional scaling); hence conjoint analysis works wonderfully well in shaping up the final product[9]. The study is based on the primary data collected from the student community through a physical questionnaire form.

4. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY: Conjoint analysis is used to understand the significance of the most likely attribute that people would like to incorporate into the new product. Conjoint analysis is a tool that helps us in understanding the levels of each attribute that can be added for the exact outcome that the customers desire. Conjoint analysis has always been used in marketing for a variety of purposes, including knowing the relative importance of attributes in the minds of the consumer. Conjoint analysis is used in intangible products like software as well as tangible products like books, furniture, or white goods[10]. The impact of things that can make using human emotions is related to the gifting of products. When products are packed based on the need and time of gifting it is critical to understand the emotions behind these products and the same to be captured while designing the same [11].

4.1 Sample Size and Respondents: Five higher Educational Institutions were selected and 10 students were the sample of each college; totaling to a sample size of 50 respondents. Out of the ten from each college five students were identified with study table and the rest of the five with out a study table at home. Hence 25 students had a study table and the other 25 students did not have a study table.

4.2 Questionnaire: It was distributed for students who were ready to participate in the survey and based on the having and not having a study table was identified and then surveyed.

5.ATTRIBUTES AND LEVELS CONSIDERED FOR THE STUDY: Out of many attributes the researcher identified mostly likely attributes that the student community preferred was based on the primary interviews conducted on a selected focus group and is as follows:

Table No:1 Attributes and Levels identified for Conjoint Analysis

SLNO	ATTRIBUTES	LEVELS
1	Colour of the study table	Flower wenge- Dark in shade
		Sandy sawline- a bit light is shade
		Mahogany- a finish that looks exactly like the mahogany tree
2	Size of the study table	2x2 square feet
		3x3 square feet
		4x4 square feet
3	Price of the study table	Rs. 5000/-
		Rs. 7500/-
		Rs. 10,000/-
4	Type of Material for the study table	Wood- full wood and seasoned wood
		Particle board- Processed material
		Plywood- Processed material

Source: Compiled by the Researcher

5.1 THE COMBINATIONAL OUTCOME: The total outcomes (CARDS) that are expected from the above attributes are $3 \times 3 \times 3 \times 3 = 81$. As these combinations are too lengthy to analyze and it makes more appropriate sense to reduce these dimensions for a more suitable format that can bring in ease of ranking. The 81 combinations create a greater feel and effect. Few of these 81 combinations are not liked by the customers and few combinations are not liked by the manufacturing company observed in the research. Hence 81 out-come of CARDS become complicated and a study is done engaging the student's group by reducing it to a total of 9 cards out of the 81 combinations,

6.REVIEW OF LITERATURE: The following literature has been revived for greater understanding of the subject under study: Furniture manufacturing is an art and it requires understanding the customer needs [12]. Customers expect customization and hence they need to be heard and understood. Customers look for uniqueness and differentiation [13]. Instore perception of furniture makes a difference in choosing the furniture. The study table should be checked by testing and using it for at least five to ten minutes to understand if it is suitable to be used at home; hence every student should check for the same [14].

7.RESULT AND DISCUSSION: The best 9 combinations have been selected based on the priority of the manufacturer and the profitability for taking it to the production level

Table No:2 Average ranking by Student respondents

Sno	Colour	Price	Size	Type of wood	Average rounded to the nearest rank	Rank
1	Flower wenge	5000	2x2	WOOD	6	
2	Flower wenge	7500	3x3	PARTICEL BOARD	9	
3	Flower wenge	10000	4x4	PLYWOOD	2	
4	Sandy sawline	5000	4x4	WOOD	4	
5	Sandy sawline	7500	2x2	PARTICLE BOARD	5	
6	Sandy sawline	10000	3x3	PLYWOOD	1	
7	Mahagany	5000	3x3	WOOD	7	
8	Mahagany	7500	4x4	PARTICLE BOARD	8	
9	Mahagany	10000	2x2	PLYWOOD	3	

Source: Compiled by the Researcher

Table No: 3 Conjoint analysis for the above table

Type	Attribute	Calculation	Summation
Colour	Flower wenge	6+9+2	=17
	Sandy Sawline	4+5+1	=10
	Mahagany	7+8+3	=18
Price	Rs.5000	6+4+7	=17
	Rs.7500	9+5+8	=22
	Rs. 10,000	2+1+3	=6
Size	2X2 square feet	6+5+3	=14
	3X3 square feet	9+1+7	=17
	4X4 square fee	2+4+8	=14
Type of Material	Wood	6+1+8	=15
	Particle board	9+4+3	=16
	Plywood	2+5+7	=4

Now we rescale and normalize the raw score

Formula Z = (X- Min Data)/ (Max Data- Min data)
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Table No: 4 The following table denotes **the z value** in an order

Attribute	Sum	Calculation	In order Z
Rs.10000	6	$(6-6)/(22-6)$	0
Sandy sawline	10	$(10-6)/(22-6)$	0.250
Plywood	14	$(14-6)/(22-6)$	0.500
4x4 Square feet	14	$(14-6)/(22-6)$	0.500
2x2 Square feet	14	$(14-6)/(22-6)$	0.500
Wood	15	$(15-6)/(22-6)$	0.562
Particle Board	16	$(16-6)/(22-6)$	0.635
3x3 square feet	17	$(17-6)/(22-6)$	0.687
Rs.5000	17	$(17-6)/(22-6)$	0.687
Flower Wenge	17	$(17-6)/(22-6)$	0.687
Mahagany	18	$(18-6)/(22-6)$	0.75
Rs.7500	22	$(22-6)/(22-6)$	1.00

Source: Compiled by the Researcher

Table No: 5 Re-organizing the original sequence

Attribute	Sum	Calculation	In order (z)
Flower wenge	17	$(17-6)/(22-6)$	0.687
Sandy sawline	10	$(10-6)/(22-6)$	0.250 (Min value)
Mahagany	18	$(18-6)/(22-6)$	0.75(Max value)
Rs.5000	17	$(17-6)/(22-6)$	0.687
Rs.7500	22	$(22-6)/(22-6)$	1.00 (Max value)
Rs.10000	6	$(6-6)/(22-6)$	0.00 (Min value)
2X2 Square feet	14	$(14-6)/(22-6)$	0.500 (Min value)
3x3 Square feet	17	$(17-6)/(22-6)$	0.687 (Max value)
4x4 Square feet	14	$(14-6)/(22-6)$	0.500 (Min value)
Wood	15	$(15-6)/(22-6)$	0.562
Particle board	16	$(16-6)/(22-6)$	0.635 (Max value)
Plywood	14	$(14-6)/(22-6)$	0.500 (Min value)

Source: Compiled by the Researcher

Table No: 6 Significance and the Outcome of the Conjoint Analysis

Type	Values of	Range	Importance	Outcome
Colour	Mahagany- Sandy sawline	$0.75-0.25=0.50$	$0.5/1.822 \times 100$	27.44
Price	Price Rs.7500- Rs.5000	$1-0= 1$	$1/1.822 \times 100$	54.88
Size	3x3 square feet- 4x4 square feet	$0.687-0.55= 0.187$	$0.187/1.822 \times 100$	10.27
Type of wood	Particle board- Plywood	$0.635-0.55=0.135$	$0.135/1.822 \times 100$	7.41

	Total	1.822		100
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Source: Compiled by the Researcher

DISCUSSION AND RESULT ANALYSIS: It is observed that the choice while buying a study table leans toward the price most of the time with a percentage of 54.88. the next most importance is given to the color of table 27.44; followed by the size 10.27 and the type of the wood 7.4. Indeed it is important to note these points while and before getting into the production of study tables. The selection was based on the attributes that students, in general, wanted to have in their home furniture. The above study states that one needs to do the groundwork for any new product that is being launched by any manufacturer and conjoint analysis is one of the approaches for the same.

8. SWOC ANALYSIS

8.1. Strength: It brings a new direction to the production process. The study creates greater advantages for any manufacturer to follow as a guideline for further new products

8.2. Weakness: The study can vary as the importance and relevance of a study table may vary according to the place and students' locations

8.3. Opportunity: There is ample scope for generating new products through conjoint analysis

8.4. Challenges: There are a few challenges in understanding and bringing down the combinations from 81 cards to 9 cards.

9. LIMITATIONS OF THE STUDY: The study only covered post-graduate students of Mangalore city colleges and hence does not cover other districts of Karnataka; hence it can not be generalized to the entire state or country. The study also is limited to one product only. The study makes one feel that price is the major attribute that people look into. The wish list of conjoint analysis is much more and all these things need to be incorporated in future research as of now they become the limitations to the study [15]. Developing conjoint analysis is much required based on Indian conditions as we are the most diversified races in the world; very essential for marketing research for a growing nation like India[16][17]. One of the facts that highlight the growth would be based on the challenges that a marketer can foresee is the commercial application of Conjoint analysis [18].

10. FUTURE SCOPE FOR FURTHER RESEARCH: As there are many methods and approaches in Conjoint analysis the same can be applied to other products in different locations in India. There is ample scope for conducting multiple furniture products with a different set of audiences or participants. It also means that new products can be created and designed for better market positioning of companies. The same can be applied to services and advanced software products too. Indeed new products are emerging and multiple new combinations can be taken forward. Solving marketing problems is the key to the growth of the economy and hence Conjoint analysis has to be learned and taught to budding management students to take up combinations or heuristics approach to a complex problem for a better solution [19].

11. CONCLUSION: One needs to develop attributes that can be further added to ensure more advanced choices that students can make. This is an attempt to ensure that we have the best outcomes as primary research into the psychology of the customers in general. Further enhancement can be done by bringing out more and more attributes with new materials as well as intangibles like warranty, durability, after-sales service, and many more. Segmentation is essential for sustenance and customization. Segmentation leads to better customization and this is the key to growth [20]

REFERENCES:

[1] Ogawa, S., & Piller, F. T. (2006). Reducing the risks of new product development. *MIT Sloan management review*, 47(2), 65.

[Google scholar ↗](#)

[2] Aagaard, J., & Storr-Paulsen, A. (1995). A comparative study of three different kinds of school furniture. *Ergonomics*, 38(5), 1025-1035.

[Google scholar ↗](#)

[3] Savanur, C. S., Altekar, C. R., & De, A. (2007). Lack of conformity between Indian classroom furniture and student dimensions: proposed future seat/table dimensions. *Ergonomics*, 50(10), 1612-1625.

[Google scholar ↗](#)

[4] Koskelo, R., Vuorikari, K., & Hänninen, O. (2007). Sitting and standing postures are corrected by adjustable furniture with lowered muscle tension in high-school students. *Ergonomics*, 50(10), 1643-1656.

[Google Scholar ↗](#)

[5] Allen, F. R., & Moyer, M. (2021). A library seating census: Gathering seating occupancy data in an academic library to reveal furniture preferences and inform future planning. *The Journal of Academic Librarianship*, 47(5), 102427.

[Google Scholar ↗](#)

[6] Chan, J. H., Selimin, M. A., & Sidek, A. A. S. (2022). Modern Study Table for Small Houses Inspired by Origami. *Research in Management of Technology and Business*, 3(1), 275-284.

[Google Scholar ↗](#)

[7] Wettschereck, D., & Aha, D. W. (1995, October). Weighting features. In *International Conference on Case-Based Reasoning* (pp. 347-358). Springer, Berlin, Heidelberg.

[Google Scholar ↗](#)

[8] Mirka, G. A. (2005). Development of an ergonomics guideline for the furniture manufacturing industry. *Applied Ergonomics*, 36(2), 241-247.

[Google Scholar ↗](#)

[9] Moore, W. L., Louviere, J. J., & Verma, R. (1999). Using conjoint analysis to help design product platforms. *Journal of Product Innovation Management: An international publication of the product development & management association*, 16(1), 27-39.

[Google Scholar ↗](#)

[10] Huber, J. (2005). Conjoint analysis: how we got here and where we are (An Update). In *Sawtooth software conference* (Vol. 98382, p. 360).

[Google Scholar ↗](#)

[11] Pentus, K., Mehine, T., & Kuusik, A. (2014). Considering emotions in product package design through combining conjoint analysis with psycho physiological measurements. *Procedia-Social and Behavioral Sciences*, 148, 280-290.

[Google Scholar](#) ↗

[12] Amin, V. S., & Kumar, A. (2022). Case Study of Furniture Manufacturing Companies. *International Journal of Case Studies in Business, IT and Education (IJCSBE)*, 6(1), 158-176.

[Google Scholar](#) ↗

[13] Amin, V. S., & Kumar, A. (2022). Case Study of VK Sofa Makers Customization Process. *International Journal of Case Studies in Business, IT and Education (IJCSBE)*, 6(1), 202-222.

[Google Scholar](#) ↗

[14] Amin, V. S., & Kumar, A. (2022). In-store Customer Perception towards Furniture in a Multi-product outlet–A Synthesis of Literature Review and Research Agenda. *International Journal of Management, Technology and Social Sciences (IJMITS)*, 7(1), 279-305.

[Google Scholar](#) ↗

[15] Bradlow, E. T. (2005). Current issues and a ‘wish list’ for conjoint analysis. *Applied stochastic models in business and industry*, 21(4-5), 319-323.

[Google Scholar](#) ↗

[16] Rao, V. R. (2008). Developments in conjoint analysis. In *Handbook of marketing decision models* (pp. 23-53). Springer, Boston, MA.

[Google Scholar](#) ↗

[17] Green, P. E., & Srinivasan, V. (1990). Conjoint analysis in marketing research: New developments and directions. *Journal of Marketing*, 54(4), 3.

[Google Scholar](#) ↗

[18] Cattin, P., & Wittink, D. R. (1982). Commercial use of conjoint analysis: A survey. *Journal of marketing*, 46(3), 44-53.

[Google Scholar](#) ↗

[19] Vriens, M. (1994). Solving marketing problems with conjoint analysis. *Journal of Marketing Management*, 10(1-3), 37-55.

[Google Scholar](#) ↗

[20] DeSarbo, W. S., Ramaswamy, V., & Cohen, S. H. (1995). Market segmentation with choice-based conjoint analysis. *Marketing Letters*, 6(2), 137-147. [Google Scholar](#) ↗

APPENDIX:

QUESTIONNAIRE

Student Name:	Branch: M.Tech, MBA, MCA, MSW
Name of the college:	E-Mail id and Contact NO:

1. Do you have a study table
Yes No
2. Given an opportunity would be interested to engage a study table and read?
Yes No
3. Kindly Rank the following as per your priority that you need as attributes in a study table:
9 being the highest and 1 being the lowest:

Sno	Colour	Price	Size	Type of wood	Your Rank
1	Flower wenge	5000	2x2	WOOD	
2	Flower wenge	7500	3x3	PARTICEL BOARD	
3	Flower wenge	10000	4x4	PLYWOOD	
4	Sandy sawline	5000	4x4	WOOD	
5	Sandy sawline	7500	2x2	PARTICLE BOARD	
6	Sandy sawline	10000	3x3	PLYWOOD	
7	Mahogany	5000	3x3	WOOD	
8	Mahogany	7500	4x4	PARTICLE BOARD	
9	Mahogany	10000	2x2	PLYWOOD	

4. Kindly mention would be interested to buy a study table:
Yes No
5. Kindly mention any other additional feature you would like a study table to have as an attribute
.....

*******THANK YOU FOR YOUR RESPONSE*******

